

EU27 Covid-19 Response Policies in place during 2020-2021. Visualization over time (month*/year)

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Legenda

Measures

ClosDaycare	Closure of educational institutions: daycare or nursery
ClosPrim	Closure of educational institutions: primary schools
ClosSec	Closure of educational institutions: secondary schools
StayHomeOrder	Stay-at-home orders for the general population (these are enforced and also referred to as 'lockdown')
WFH	Teleworking recommendation or workplace closures

ECDC, (2021), Covid-19: Policy responses across Europe [Database]. Version 23 September 2021.

Source: <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/download-data-response-measures-covid-19>.

**Note: all periods are rounded to 2 weeks for simplification.*

Country	Measure	03/20	04/20	05/20	06/20	07/20	08/20	09/20	10/20	11/20	12/20	1/21	2/21	3/21	4/21	5/21	6/21	7/21	8/21
Austria	ClosDaycare																		
	ClosPrim																		
	ClosSec																		
	StayHomeOrder																		
	WFH																		
Belgium	ClosDaycare																		
	ClosPrim																		
	ClosSec																		
	StayHomeOrder																		
	WFH																		

Bulgaria	ClosDaycare																			
	ClosPrim																			
	ClosSec																			
	StayHomeOrder																			
	WFH																			
Country	Measure	03/20	04/20	05/20	06/20	07/20	08/20	09/20	10/20	11/20	12/20	1/21	2/21	3/21	4/21	5/21	6/21	7/21	8/21	
Croatia	ClosDaycare																			
	ClosPrim																			
	ClosSec																			
	StayHomeOrder																			
	WFH																			
Cyprus	ClosDaycare																			
	ClosPrim																			
	ClosSec																			
	StayHomeOrder																			
	WFH																			
Czechia	ClosDaycare																			
	ClosPrim																			
	ClosSec																			
	StayHomeOrder																			
	WFH																			
Denmark	ClosDaycare																			
	ClosPrim																			
	ClosSec																			
	StayHomeOrder																			
	WFH																			
Estonia	ClosDaycare																			
	ClosPrim																			
	ClosSec																			
	StayHomeOrder																			

	WFH																				
Country	Measure	03/20	04/20	05/20	06/20	07/20	08/20	09/20	10/20	11/20	12/20	1/21	2/21	3/21	4/21	5/21	6/21	7/21	8/21		
Finland	ClosDaycare																				
	ClosPrim																				
	ClosSec																				
	StayHomeOrder																				
	WFH																				
Francia	ClosDaycare																				
	ClosPrim																				
	ClosSec																				
	StayHomeOrder																				
	WFH																				
Germany	ClosDaycare																				
	ClosPrim																				
	ClosSec																				
	StayHomeOrder																				
	WFH																				
Greece	ClosDaycare																				
	ClosPrim																				
	ClosSec																				
	StayHomeOrder																				
	WFH																				
Hungary	ClosDaycare																				
	ClosPrim																				
	ClosSec																				
	StayHomeOrder																				
	WFH																				
Country	Measure	03/20	04/20	05/20	06/20	07/20	08/20	09/20	10/20	11/20	12/20	1/21	2/21	3/21	4/21	5/21	6/21	7/21	8/21		

Country	Measure	03/20	04/20	05/20	06/20	07/20	08/20	09/20	10/20	11/20	12/20	1/21	2/21	3/21	4/21	5/21	6/21	7/21	8/21
Netherlands	ClosDaycare																		
	ClosPrim																		
	ClosSec																		
	StayHomeOrder																		
	WFH																		
Poland	ClosDaycare																		
	ClosPrim																		
	ClosSec																		
	StayHomeOrder																		
	WFH																		
Portugal	ClosDaycare																		
	ClosPrim																		
	ClosSec																		
	StayHomeOrder																		
	WFH																		
Romania	ClosDaycare																		
	ClosPrim																		
	ClosSec																		
	StayHomeOrder																		
	WFH																		
Slovakia	ClosDaycare																		
	ClosPrim																		
	ClosSec																		
	StayHomeOrder																		
	WFH																		
Country	Measure	03/20	04/20	05/20	06/20	07/20	08/20	09/20	10/20	11/20	12/20	1/21	2/21	3/21	4/21	5/21	6/21	7/21	8/21

